

**Notes—Forthcoming Energy and Climate Law
Quarterly—2021**

NON-STATE ACTORS AND CLIMATE LITIGATION: THE FRENCH
STATE IS CONDEMNED FOR NON-COMPLIANCE WITH ITS AIR
POLLUTION OBLIGATIONS

*[Conseil d’Etat [hereinafter referred to
as the Council of State] Assembly,
10 July 2020—n°428409]*

The Council of State ruled on the case on 12 July 2017, in which it ordered the government to draw up and implement air quality plans likely to reduce nitrogen dioxide concentrations. Pursuant in particular to the provisions of Article R. 221-1 of the Environment Code, these plans should cover thirteen areas of the territory. In this respect, on the basis of the latest available data, the reduction of concentrations should apply to twelve urban areas, while the reduction of fine particles PM10 should apply to three areas. By this decision, the Council annulled the implicit decisions of the President of the Republic, the Prime Minister and the Ministers responsible for the environment and health, refusing to take all appropriate measures and to draw up plans in accordance with Article 23 of Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe, the apparent aim of which was to reduce concentrations of fine particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide throughout the national territory to below the limit values laid down in Annex XI to that Directive.

In addition, the Council enjoined the Prime Minister and the Minister for the Environment to take all measures deemed useful to draw up and implement, for each of the area listed in point 9 of the grounds for the decision, an air quality plan to reduce concentrations of nitrogen dioxide and fine particles PM10 below the limit values set by Article R. 221-1 of the Environment Code in the shortest possible time

and to send it to the European Commission before 31 March 2018.

In a letter dated 20 June 2018, the Delegate for the Enforcement of Court Decisions of the Report and Studies Section of the Council of State brought to the attention of the government, in particular the Minister of State, Minister for Ecological Transition and Solidarity, to notify it of the measures taken by the State services to ensure the enforcement of this decision. In return, the Minister of State, Minister of Ecological and Solidarity Transition listed the series of measures adopted by the State to this end in his observations registered on 16 July 2018.

On 2 October 2018, a case is brought before the Council of State by a coalition of associations working in the field of environmental protection. In the application, the association Les amis de la Terre - France was the first organisation cited as applicant, with some sixty associations including a few individuals. The application requested the Council of State to firstly note that the decision of 12 July 2017 of the Council of State had not been executed by 31 March 2018 ; secondly, to impose a penalty payment of 100,000 euros per day of delay on the State, if it does not justify having taken measures to ensure the execution of the decision of 12 July 2017 within a period of one month from the notification of this decision; finally, to charge the State with the sum of 3,000 euros under Article L. 761-1 of the code of administrative justice.

On the admissibility of the application, the Council of State had dismissed the standing of certain associations because of their corporate purpose, which it could not consider as interested parties by virtue of the provisions of Articles L. 911-4 and R. 931-2 of the code of administrative justice, and therefore the request for a penalty payment was inadmissible as far as they were concerned. However, the Council had held that, with regard to the association Les amis de la Terre -France, the application was admissible, as it was a party to the proceedings that gave rise to the decision of 12 July 2017 and could be considered as interested parties

along with the other natural and legal persons claiming damages.

As to the merits, it was pointed out that the Government had adopted and published fourteen roadmaps, which had been transmitted to the European Commission. The plans give a detailed picture of the concrete actions to be undertaken in each area, the timetables for their implementation and the necessary means to be mobilised. However, the plans lacked precision as regards the estimated improvement in air quality and the deadlines for achieving these objectives, which - in many respects - was contrary to the requirements laid down in Annex XV of Directive 2008/50/EC of 21 May 2008 and transposed into French law in Article R. 222-15 of the Environment Code.

Subsequently, the Government had initiated a review of the plans applicable to two areas, firstly, the new Arve Valley plan, which incorporated credible measurements and modelling of their impact, making it possible to expect compliance with the limit values by 2022, deemed to be in line with the decision of 12 July 2017, on the other hand, the new Ile de France plan, which merely sets the year 2025 as the target date for returning below the limit values, without any justification as to why the requirement for the shortest possible period of exceedance would have been met before that date. As of that date, the revision of the other eleven plans had not been undertaken.

The decision states that, 'the various elements produced during the jurisdictional procedure do not make it possible to establish that the cumulative effects of the various measures adopted following the decision of 12 July 2017 will make it possible to bring the concentration levels of these two pollutants below these limit values in the shortest possible time'. These are in particular the administrative monitoring areas in which the concentration limit values for NO₂ and PM₁₀ set by Article R. 221-1 of the Environment Code remain exceeded. Also with regard to certain areas, such as the Grenoble and Lyon ZAS, for the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, Strasbourg and Reims, for the Grand-Est region, Marseille-Aix, for the Provence-

Alpes-Côte-d'Azur region, Toulouse, for the Occitanie region and Paris, for the Ile-de-France region, the PM10 concentration rates, at the date of the decision, do not make it possible to conclude that the State had taken sufficient measures to ensure the full implementation of its decision of 12 July 2017.

In view of the above, the State had not taken the measures likely to ensure the implementation of the Council of State's decision of 12 July 2017, with the exception of the Arve Valley plan, concerning the persistent exceeding of the limit values for CO2 and particle concentrations. Moreover, due to the time that has elapsed since the intervention of the 2017 decision, but also to the importance attached to effective compliance with the requirements arising from European Union law, and above all to the seriousness of the consequences of the partial failure to implement it, which concern both public health and the environment, the State's responsibility for failing to implement this decision concerning its internal obligations in terms of the environment, as well as its international obligations with regard to its compliance with European Union law, should be retained.

The Council of State ordered the French State to pay a periodic penalty payment of 10 million euros per half-year if, within six months of notification of the decision of 10 July 2020, it does not justify having implemented the decision of the Council of State of 12 July 2017. Likewise, the Prime Minister will have to provide the Report and Studies Section of the Council of State with a copy of the acts justifying the measures taken to implement the decision of 12 July 2017. Finally, the State will have to pay the association Les Amis de la Terre - France et consorts, a total sum of 3,000 euros.

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[This research is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement n° 845118].